

SPECIFIC FEATURES OF THE EDUCATIONAL PROCESS IN PRESCHOOL EDUCATION ON THE BASIS OF DUAL EDUCATION

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Annotation The organization of the preschool educational process on the basis of dual education is of great importance in increasing the effectiveness of education. This system combines theoretical knowledge with practice, ensures the active participation of children and contributes to the development of their independent thinking and creative abilities.

Keywords: Dual education, preschool education, educational process, practical and theoretical knowledge, interactive education, pedagogical approach, child development, independent thinking, creative abilities.

Nowadays, modernization of the education system and improvement of the quality of education are one of the important issues. The dual education system is widely used in developed countries and is based on the combination of education and practice. This article analyzes the specific features of the educational process in preschool education based on the dual system. The dual education system is an innovative approach that combines theoretical and practical education, in which students (educators) receive theoretical knowledge in an educational institution and learn practical skills in a real environment. This model can also be used in the preschool education system and have a positive impact on the development of children.

The introduction of the dual system in preschool education serves to strengthen the social and psychological readiness of children. This system includes the following elements:

1. Theoretical education

- ❖ Activities that support the mental development of children
- ❖ Teaching by educators and educators using scientifically based methodologies
- ❖ Use of didactic games, interactive methods

2. Practical education

- ❖ Formation of life skills (self-service, teamwork)
- ❖ Providing initial concepts of various professions
- ❖ Direct acquaintance with nature and the social environment

Dual education is successfully used in many developed countries, in particular in Germany, Switzerland and Austria. Dual education has several positive aspects. Firstly, during their studies, students not only get acquainted with theoretical knowledge, but also have the opportunity to test their knowledge in a real work environment. This increases their readiness for practice. Secondly, students gain work experience by participating in practical work. This, of course, gives them a great advantage in the labor market. Also, students who study in dual education often have the opportunity to work in the organization where they studied after graduation, because they become familiar with the work processes of the organization. In dual education, students are often paid a scholarship or salary, which ensures their financial independence.

The dual system helps to effectively organize educational processes aimed at developing these competencies. The dual system combines theoretical knowledge with practical activities. This creates an opportunity for preschool students to apply pedagogical methods in practice and helps to

understand knowledge more deeply. Preschool children are considered to be the period when cognitive abilities develop most actively. It is important to use innovative methods and approaches to develop them. The methodology based on the dual system increases children's interest and forms their need for knowledge. Educators working in the preschool education system not only should have not only theoretical knowledge, but also practical skills. Through the dual system, students gain experience in real conditions during the learning process. Approaches aimed at developing cognitive competencies in children increase the quality of education, and dual system methods in this process provide high efficiency. The dual system provides constant monitoring of the educational process, flexibility to identify problems and solve them. This makes pedagogical activities more effective. The relevance of the methodology for developing cognitive competencies for preschool students through the dual system is associated with the development trends of the modern education system. Its necessity is determined by improving the quality of education, the formation of practical skills, and the effective organization of the cognitive process of children. This methodology is of great benefit not only for teachers, but also for children.

The organization of preschool education on the basis of the dual system has a positive impact on the intellectual, social and physical development of children. Through cooperation between educational institutions and practice, the knowledge and skills of the future generation are further strengthened. Therefore, it is necessary to further develop scientific and methodological research on the implementation of this system.

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